

SOME PRIMITIVE IDEMPOTENTS IN R_{16p^n}

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ABSTRACT

Let F be a finite field of prime power order q , where q is of the form $16k + 5$. If q is primitive root modulo p^n , then the semi-simple group algebra FG of the cyclic group G of order $16p^n$ over F , where p is an odd prime and $n \geq 1$, has $16n + 7$ primitive idempotents. Explicit expressions for these primitive idempotents are obtained.

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1. Introduction

Let $F = GF(q)$ be a finite field of prime power order q and G be a cyclic group of order m such that $\text{g.c.d.}(m, q) = 1$. Then FG , the group algebra of the cyclic group G over F , is semi-simple and has only a finite number of primitive idempotents which equals the number of cyclotomic cosets modulo m . Let t be the multiplicative order of q modulo m , then $1 \leq t \leq \phi(m)$ [4]. If $t = \phi(m)$ and $m = 2, 4, p^n, 2p^n$, the complete sets of primitive idempotents were calculated by Pruthi and Arora [1, 6]. The minimal quadratic residue cyclic codes of length p^n were obtained by Batra and Arora [3]. The minimal cyclic codes of length $p^n q$ were discussed by Bakshi and Raka [2].

Let $S = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, 16p^n - 1\}$. For $a, b \in S$, the relation $a \equiv bq^i \pmod{16p^n}$ for some integer $i \geq 0$ partitions S into $16n + 7$ q -cyclotomic cosets given by

(i) $\Omega_{ap^n} = \{ap^n\}, a = 0, 4, 8, 4\lambda$

- (ii) $\Omega_{bp^n} = \{bp^n, bp^nq\}, b = 2, 2\lambda$
- (iii) $\Omega_{cp^n} = \{cp^n, cp^nq, cp^nq^2, cp^nq^3\}, b = 1, \lambda$
- (iv) $\Omega_{dp^i} = \{dp^i, dp^iq, \dots, dp^iq^{\phi(p^{n-i})-1}\}, d \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, \mu, 2\mu, v, 2v, \chi, \psi, \tau\}$

where $\lambda = 1 + 2p^n, \mu = 1 + 4p^n, v = 1 + 6p^n, \chi = 1 + 8p^n, \psi = 1 + 10p^n, \pi = 1 + 12p^n, \tau = 1 + 14p^n$.

The primitive idempotent corresponding to the cyclotomiccosets Ω_{tp^n} for $t = 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda$ and Ω_{sp^i} for $s = 2, 4, 8, 16, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, 2\mu, 2v$ are obtained in Section 2 in Theorems 2.1.1-2.7.1. In Section 3, we discussed the primitive idempotent corresponding to the cyclotomiccosets Ω_{sp^i} for $s \in \{1, \lambda, \mu, v, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$ in Theorem 3.1.1.

2. Primitive Idempotent Corresponding to the CyclotomicCosets

Ω_{tp^n} for $t = 0, 1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda$ and Ω_{sp^i} for $s = 2, 4, 8, 16, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, 2\mu, 2v$

The primitive idempotent $\theta_s(x)$ corresponding to Ω_s in R_{16p^n} is $\theta_s(x) = \frac{1}{16p^n} \sum_{i=0}^{16p^n-1} \epsilon_i^s x^i$, where

$$\epsilon_i^s = \sum_{s \in \Omega_s} \alpha^{-is}. \text{ Also denote } \bar{C}_s = \sum_{s \in \Omega_s} x^s. \text{ [28].}$$

So, we have

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_s(x) = & \frac{1}{16p^n} [\epsilon_0^s \bar{C}_0 + \epsilon_{p^n}^s \bar{C}_{p^n} + \epsilon_{2p^n}^s \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \epsilon_{4p^n}^s \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \epsilon_{8p^n}^s \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \epsilon_{\lambda p^n}^s \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \epsilon_{2\lambda p^n}^s \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} \\ & + \epsilon_{4\lambda p^n}^s \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \epsilon_{p^i}^s \bar{C}_{p^i} + \epsilon_{2p^i}^s \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \epsilon_{4p^i}^s \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \epsilon_{8p^i}^s \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \epsilon_{16p^i}^s \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \epsilon_{\lambda p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} \\ & + \epsilon_{2\lambda p^i}^s \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \epsilon_{4\lambda p^i}^s \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \epsilon_{\mu p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \epsilon_{2\mu p^i}^s \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \epsilon_{vp^i}^s \bar{C}_{vp^i} + \epsilon_{2vp^i}^s \bar{C}_{2vp^i} + \epsilon_{\chi p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} \\ & + \epsilon_{\psi p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \epsilon_{\pi p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \epsilon_{\tau p^i}^s \bar{C}_{\tau p^i}] \end{aligned} \tag{2.1}$$

2.1. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_0 and Ω_{8p^n} .

Lemma 2.1.1. If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $-\Omega_{8p^n} = \Omega_{8p^n}$.

Proof. Since $8p^n \equiv -8p^n \pmod{16p^n}$, therefore the result holds.

Theorem 2.1.1. The primitive idempotent $\theta_0(x)$ and $\theta_{8p^n}(x)$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_0(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\{\bar{C}_0 + \bar{C}_{p^n} + \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n}\} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{\bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} \\ &\quad + \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i}\}] \\ \theta_{8p^n}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\{\bar{C}_0 - \bar{C}_{p^n} + \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n}\} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{\bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} \\ &\quad + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - \bar{C}_{\tau p^i}\}]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. For $s = 0$, then $\epsilon_k^0 = \sum_{s \in \Omega_0} \alpha^{-ks} = \alpha^{k_0} = 1$ for all $0 \leq k \leq 16p^n - 1$. Therefore, replacing ϵ_k^0 by 1 in

(2.1), we get the required expression. For $s = 8p^n$ in (2.1), so we need to compute $\epsilon_{ap^n}^{8p^n}$ and $\epsilon_{bp^n}^{8p^n}$ for $a \in \{0, 1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda\}$ and $b \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, \mu, 2\mu, \nu, 2\nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$.

Since $-\Omega_{8p^n} = \Omega_{8p^n}$, so $\epsilon_k^{8p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^n}} \alpha^{-ks} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^n}} \alpha^{ks} = \alpha^{8p^n k}$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_0^{8p^n} &= \alpha^{0 \cdot 8p^n} = 1 = \epsilon_{2p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{4p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{8p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{2p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{4p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{8p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{16p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{2\lambda p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{4\lambda p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{2\mu p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{2\nu p^i}^{8p^n}, \\ \epsilon_{p^n}^{8p^n} &= \alpha^{8p^{2n}} = -1 = \epsilon_{\lambda p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\mu p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\nu p^n}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\mu p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\nu p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\chi p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\psi p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\pi p^i}^{8p^n} = \epsilon_{\tau p^i}^{8p^n}. \end{aligned}$$

By substituting all these in (2.1), we get the required expression.

2.2. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_{p^n} and $\Omega_{\lambda p^n}$.

Lemma 2.2.1. If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $-\Omega_{p^n} = \Omega_{\lambda p^n}$

Proof. Proof of these are trivial.

Theorem 2.2.1. The primitive idempotent θ_{p^n} and $\theta_{\lambda p^n}$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\theta_{p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{16p^n} [4\bar{C}_0 - 4\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{4p^n} - 4\bar{C}_{8p^n} - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{4\alpha^{4p^{i+n}}\bar{C}_{4p^i} + 4\bar{C}_{8p^i} - 4\bar{C}_{16p^i} - 4\alpha^{4p^{i+n}}\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i}\}]$$

$$\alpha_{\lambda p^n}(x) = \frac{1}{16p^n} [4\bar{C}_0 + 4\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{4p^n} - 4\bar{C}_{8p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{4\alpha^{4p^{i+n}}\bar{C}_{4p^i} - 4\bar{C}_{8p^i} + 4\bar{C}_{16p^i} - 4\alpha^{4p^{i+n}}\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i}\}]$$

Proof. For $s = p^n$ in (2.1), so we need to compute $\epsilon_{ap^n}^{p^n}$ and $\epsilon_{bp^i}^{p^n}$ for $a \in \{0, 1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda\}$ and $b \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, \mu, 2\mu, \nu, 2\nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$.

Since $-\Omega_{p^n} = \Omega_{\lambda p^n}$, so

$$\epsilon_k^{p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^n}} \alpha^{-ks} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{ks} + \alpha^{\lambda p^n k} + \alpha^{\lambda p^n q k} + \alpha^{\lambda p^n q^2 k} + \alpha^{\lambda p^n q^3 k}$$

Therefore,

$$\epsilon_0^{p^n} = \alpha^{0 \cdot \lambda p^n} + \alpha^{0 \cdot \lambda p^n q} + \alpha^{0 \cdot \lambda p^n q^2} + \alpha^{0 \cdot \lambda p^n q^3} = 1 + 1 + 1 + 1 = 4 = -\epsilon_{8p^n}^{p^n} = -\epsilon_{8p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{16p^i}^{p^n},$$

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{p^n}^{p^n} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{p^n s} = 0 = \epsilon_{2p^n}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^n}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{2\lambda p^n}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{2p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{2\lambda p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\mu p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{2\mu p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\nu p^i}^{p^n} \\ &= \epsilon_{2\nu p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\chi p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\psi p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\pi p^i}^{p^n} = \epsilon_{\tau p^i}^{p^n}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\epsilon_{4p^n}^{p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{4p^n s} = -4\alpha^{4p^{2n}} = \epsilon_{4\lambda p^n}^{p^n},$$

$$\epsilon_{4p^i}^{p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = -4\alpha^{4p^{n+i}} = \epsilon_{4\lambda p^i}^{p^n}.$$

By substituting all these in (2.1), we get the required expression.

For $s = lp^n$ in (2.1), so we need to compute $\epsilon_{ap^n}^{\lambda p^n}$ and $\epsilon_{bp^i}^{\lambda p^n}$ for $a \in \{0, 1, 2, 4, 8, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda\}$ and $b \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, \lambda, 2\lambda, 4\lambda, \mu, 2\mu, \nu, 2\nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$.

Since $-\Omega_{\lambda p^n} = \Omega_{p^n}$, so

$$\epsilon_k^{\lambda p^n} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{-ks} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^n}} \alpha^{ks} = \alpha^{p^n k} + \alpha^{p^n q k} + \alpha^{p^n q^2 k} + \alpha^{p^n q^3 k}$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_0^{\lambda p^n} &= \alpha^{0.p^n} + \alpha^{0.p^n q} + \alpha^{0.p^n q^2} + \alpha^{0.p^n q^3} = 1+1+1+1 = 4 = -\epsilon_{8p^n}^{\lambda p^n} = -\epsilon_{8p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{16p^i}^{\lambda p^n}, \\ \epsilon_{p^n}^{\lambda p^n} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^n}} \alpha^{p^n s} = 0 = \epsilon_{2p^n}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^n}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{2\lambda p^n}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{2p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{2\lambda p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\mu p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{2\mu p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\nu p^i}^{\lambda p^n} \\ &= \epsilon_{2\nu p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\lambda p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\psi p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\pi p^i}^{\lambda p^n} = \epsilon_{\tau p^i}^{\lambda p^n}, \\ \epsilon_{4p^n}^{\lambda p^n} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^n}} \alpha^{4p^n s} = 4\alpha^{4p^{2n}} = -\epsilon_{4\lambda p^n}^{\lambda p^n}, \\ \epsilon_{4p^i}^{\lambda p^n} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^n}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = 4\alpha^{4p^{n+i}} = -\epsilon_{4\lambda p^i}^{\lambda p^n}. \end{aligned}$$

By substituting all these in (2.1), we get the required expression.

2.3. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_{2p^n} and $\Omega_{2\lambda p^n}$.

Lemma 2.3.1. If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $-\Omega_{2p^n} = \Omega_{2\lambda p^n}$.

Proof. Proof of these are trivial.

Theorem 2.3.1. The primitive idempotent θ_{2p^n} and $\theta_{2\lambda p^n}$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{2p^n}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [2\bar{C}_0 - 2\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + 2\bar{C}_{8p^n} + 2\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - 2\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} - \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2p^i} \\ &\quad + 2\bar{C}_{4p^i} - 2\bar{C}_{8p^i} - 2\bar{C}_{16p^i} - 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + 2\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i}\}] \\ \theta_{2\lambda p^n}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [2\bar{C}_0 + 2\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + 2\bar{C}_{8p^n} - 2\alpha^{4p^{2n}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - 2\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} + \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2p^i} \\ &\quad - 2\bar{C}_{4p^i} + 2\bar{C}_{8p^i} + 2\bar{C}_{16p^i} - 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - 2\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - 2\alpha^{4p^{n+i}}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i}\}] \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof is on similar lines as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

2.4. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_{4p^n} and $\Omega_{4\lambda p^n}$.

Lemma 2.4.1. If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, then $-\Omega_{4p^n} = \Omega_{4\lambda p^n}$.

Proof. Proof of trivial.

Theorem 2.4.1. The primitive idempotent θ_{4p^n} and $\theta_{4\lambda p^n}$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{4p^n}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{4p^{2n}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{2n}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \\ &- \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \\ &+ \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \}] \\ \theta_{4\lambda p^n}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{4p^{2n}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{2n}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \\ &+ \sum_{i=0}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{p^i} - \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} \\ &- \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{n+i}} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \}. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof is on similar lines as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

2.5. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_{8p^i} and Ω_{16p^i} .

Lemma 2.5.1. If p is an odd prime, s is some positive integer, θ is primitive p^s th root of unity in some extension field of $GF(q)$, then

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^s)-1} \theta^{qt} = \begin{cases} -1 & \text{for } s = 1 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Proof. As $\phi(p^s)$ is the order of q modulo p^s , therefore, $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, \phi(p^s)-1\}$ is a reduced residue system modulo p^s . So

$$\sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^s)-1} \theta^{qt} = \sum_{t=1}^{p^s} \theta^t - \sum_{t=1, p/t}^{p^s} \theta^t = \sum_{t=0}^{p^s-1} \theta^t - \sum_{t=1}^{p^s-1} \theta^{pt}$$

If $s > 1$, then $\sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^s)-1} \theta^{qt} = \frac{\theta^{p^s} - 1}{\theta - 1} - \frac{(\theta^p)^{p^{s-1}} - 1}{\theta^p - 1}$, since θ is a primitive p^s th root of unit $\theta \neq 1$ and as $\theta^{p^{s-1}} \neq 1$ the above sums reduces to zero. However, for $s = 1$, the first sum term reduces to zero and second term reduces to 1. Hence the required result is obtained.

Lemma 2.5.2. If δ is some primitive $2p^k$ th root of unity in some extension field of $GF(q)$ for an odd prime p , and positive integer k , then

$$\sum_{s=0}^{\phi(2p^k)-1} \delta^{q^s} = \begin{cases} 1, & k = 1 \\ 0, & k \geq 2. \end{cases}$$

Proof. As $\{1, q, q^2, \dots, q^{\phi(2p^k)-1}\}$ is a reduced residue system modulo $2p^k$. So

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s=0}^{\phi(2p^k)-1} \delta^{q^s} &= \sum_{s=1}^{2p^k} \delta^s - \sum_{s=1/2, s}^{2p^k} \delta^s - \sum_{s=1, p/s}^{2p^k} \delta^s + \sum_{s=1, 2p/s}^{2p^k} \delta^s \\ &= \sum_{s=1}^{2p^k} \delta^s - \sum_{s=1}^{p^k} \delta^{2s} - \sum_{s=1}^{2p^{k-1}} \delta^{ps} + \sum_{s=1}^{p^{k-1}} \delta^{2ps}. \end{aligned}$$

Since δ is primitive $2p^k$ th root of unity, therefore $\delta \neq 1, \delta^2 \neq 1, \delta^p \neq 1$ and $\delta^{2p} \neq 1$. Hence,

$$\sum_{s=1}^{2p^k} \delta^s = \frac{\delta(\delta^{2p^k} - 1)}{\delta - 1} = 0, \forall k$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{p^k} \delta^{2s} = \frac{\delta^2(\delta^{2p^k} - 1)}{\delta^2 - 1} = 0, \forall k$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{2p^{k-1}} \delta^{ps} = \frac{\delta^p(\delta^{2p^k} - 1)}{\delta^p - 1} = 0, \forall k$$

$$\sum_{s=1}^{p^{k-1}} \delta^{2ps} = \begin{cases} \frac{\delta^{2p}(\delta^{2p^{k-1}} - 1)}{\delta^{2p} - 1} = 0 & \text{if } k > 1 \\ \delta^{2p} = 1 & \text{if } k \geq 2 \end{cases}$$

Therefore, the required result holds.

Lemma 2.5.3. If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ then $(1 + 14p^n) q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{16p^n}$

Proof. Since $(1+14p^n) \equiv 1 \pmod{p^n}$ and $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$. Therefore, $(1+14p^n)q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{p^n}$.

Further $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$ and $16k + 5$ is the form of q , therefore $q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}}$ is of the form $16s+1$. Also $p^n =$

$8k+1$, so $(1+14p^n)q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} = [1+14(8k+1)](16s+1) \equiv -1 \pmod{16}$. Also, $\text{g.c.d.}(16, p^n) = 1$, thus $(1 + 14p^n)$

$q^{\frac{\phi(p^n)}{2}} \equiv -1 \pmod{16p^n}$.

Remark. Above lemma results in the following:

“If $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{8}$, then $-\Omega_i = \Omega_{\pi}$.”

Lemma 2.5.4. For $0 \leq j \leq n$,

$$(i) \Omega_{2^{\nu}p^j} = -\Omega_{2p^j} \quad (ii) \Omega_{4^{\lambda}p^j} = -\Omega_{4p^j} \quad (iii) \Omega_{8^{\rho}p^j} = -\Omega_{8p^j} \quad (iv) \Omega_{16^{\rho}p^j} = -\Omega_{16p^j}.$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using the Lemma 2.5.3.

Lemma 2.5.5. If $r \in \{1, 2, 4, 8, 16, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, \psi, \xi, \tau\}$, then for $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$,

$$r\Omega_{16p^j} = \Omega_{16p^j} = \Omega_{16p^j}.$$

Proof. Trivially it holds.

Lemma 2.5.6. If $0 \leq i \leq n$ and $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\mu p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\nu p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} \\ &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\psi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{8p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = \begin{cases} -\phi(p^{n-j}), & i+j \leq n \\ p^{n-j-1}, & i+j = n-1 \\ 0, & i+j < n-1 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Since $\sum_{s \in 4p^j} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1} \alpha^{8p^{i+j}q^t} = \sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1} \alpha^{8p^{i+j}q^t}$. By expressing all other sums in the

hypothesis are equal.

Let $\delta = \alpha^{8p^{i+j}}$. Then $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} = \sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1} \alpha^{8p^{i+j} q^t} = \sum_{t=0}^{\phi(p^{n-j})-1} \delta^{q^t}$. For $i + j \geq n$, or when $i = n$, then by

assumption $\delta = -1$. So, $\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} = -\phi(p^{n-j})$. For $i + j \leq n - 1$, by assumption δ becomes $2p^{n-i-j}$ th

root of unity this time and so $\delta^{q^l} = \delta^{q^r}$ iff $q^l \equiv q^r \pmod{2p^{n-i-j}}$ iff $l \equiv r \pmod{\phi(p^{2n-i-j})}$. Now q is a primitive root modulo $2p^{n-i-j}$ as it is a primitive root modulo p^{n-i-j} . Using lemma 2.5.2, the required result is obtained.

Lemma 2.5.7. If $0 \leq i \leq n$ and $0 \leq j \leq n - 1$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2p^j}} \alpha^{8p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} \\ &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{16p^i s} = \begin{cases} \phi(p^{n-j}), & i + j \geq n \\ -p^{n-j-1}, & i + j = n - 1 \\ 0, & i + j < n - 1 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Using similar arguments as of lemma 2.5.6 and lemma 2.5.1, the following is obtained.

Theorem 2.5.1. The primitive idempotent Ω_{8p^i} and Ω_{16p^i} in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{8p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \bar{C}_{p^n} + \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \\ &\sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \bar{C}_{p^i} - \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} \\ &+ \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{p^i} - \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} \\ &+ \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \}] \\ \theta_{16p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \bar{C}_{p^n} + \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \\ &\sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} \} \end{aligned}$$

SOME PRIMITIVE IDEMPOTENTS IN R_{16p^n}

$$+\bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} \\ + \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + \bar{C}_{\tau p^i})]$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using lemma 2.5.6 and 2.5.7 and using the similar procedure as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

2.6. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to Ω_{4p^i} and $\Omega_{4\lambda p^i}$.

In some extension field of GF(q), let α be a fixed primitive $16p^n$ th root of unit. Define

$$C_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^i}} \alpha^s \text{ for } 0 \leq i \leq n-1.$$

$$\text{Since } (C_i)^q = \left(p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^i}} \alpha^s \right)^q = (p^i)^q \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^i}} \alpha^{qs} = (p^i)^q \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^i q}} \alpha^s.$$

However, $(p^i)^q = p^i$ and $q\Omega_{4p^i} = \Omega_{4p^i}$. Therefore, $(C_i)^q = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{4p^i}} \alpha^s = C_i$ and so $C_i \in GF(q)$.

Lemma 2.6.1. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} \\ = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{4p^i s} = \begin{cases} \phi(p^{n-j})\alpha^{4p^{i+j}}, & i+j \geq n, j < n \\ 2\alpha^{4p^{i+j}}, & i+j \geq n, j = n \\ \frac{1}{p^j} C_{i+j}, & i+j < n-1 \end{cases}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of lemma 2.5.6.

Theorem 2.6.1. The primitive idempotent Ω_{4p^i} and $\Omega_{4\lambda p^i}$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\theta_{4p^i}(x) = \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 & +\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \bar{C}_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} \\
 & + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{p^i} + \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} \\
 & + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\
 & - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{2p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{4p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^{n-j-1}})] \\
 \theta_{4\lambda p^i}(x) & = \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} \\
 & + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\
 & - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ 4p^{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} \\
 & + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} \\
 & + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i})]
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using lemma 2.6.1 and the similar procedure as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

2.7. Primitive Idempotent corresponding to the cyclotomic cosets $\Omega_{2p^i}, \Omega_{2\lambda p^i}, \Omega_{2\mu p^i}$ and $\Omega_{2\nu p^i}$.

Define $B_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2p^i}} \alpha^s$ and $D_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\lambda p^i}} \alpha^s$ for $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$.

Then, as discussed previously $B_i, D_i \in GF(q)$.

Lemma 2.7.1. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{2p^i s} = \begin{cases} \phi(p^{n-j}) \alpha^{2p^{i+j}}, & i+j \geq n, j < n \\ 2\alpha^{2p^{i+j}}, & i+j \geq n, j = n \\ \frac{1}{p^j} B_{i+j}, & i+j < n-1 \end{cases}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of lemma 2.5.6.

Lemma 2.7.2. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n - 1$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\mu p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\tau p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\nu p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{2\mu p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } i + j \geq n \\ \frac{1}{p^j} D_{i+j}, & \text{if } i + j \leq n - 1 \end{cases}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained on similar lines as that of lemma 2.5.6.

Theorem 2.7.1. The primitive idempotent $\Omega_{2p^i}, \Omega_{2\lambda p^i}, \Omega_{2\mu p^i}$ and $\Omega_{2\nu p^i}$ in R_{16p^n} are having the following expressions:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{2p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} \\ &\quad - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \\ &\quad + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} \\ &\quad + \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \\ &\quad + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \} + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{4p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^{n-j-1}})] \\ \theta_{2\lambda p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{2\nu p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} \\ &\quad - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \\ &\quad - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{p^i} \\ &\quad - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \\ &\quad + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \} + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{4p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^{n-j-1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \theta_{2\mu p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j})\{\bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\
 &+ \alpha^{4p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n}\} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=1}^{n-j-1} \{D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2p^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\mu p^i} \\
 &+ C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\tau p^i}\} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \\
 &\sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{\alpha^{4p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{2p^i} + \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \\
 &+ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}}\bar{C}_{\tau p^i}\} + p^{n-j-1}(\bar{C}_{4p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} \\
 &- \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^{n-j-1}})] \\
 \theta_{2\nu p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j})\{\bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} + \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} \\
 &- \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n}\} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - B_{i-j}\bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \\
 &- D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - C_{i+j}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + B_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\pi p^i} - D_{i+j}\bar{C}_{\tau p^i}\} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{\alpha^{2p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{p^i} \\
 &+ \alpha^{4p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{2p^i} - \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \\
 &+ \alpha^{2p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+1}}\bar{C}_{\pi p^i}\} + p^{n-j-1}(\bar{C}_{4p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}} + \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^{n-j-1}})]
 \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using lemmas 2.7.1 and 2.7.2 and similar procedure as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

3. Primitive Idempotent Corresponding to the Cyclotomic Cosets

$$\Omega_{sp^i} \text{ for } s \in \{1, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$$

In this section, the expression for primitive idempotents corresponding to the cyclotomic cosets Ω_{sp^i} for $s \in \{1, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$ are obtained.

3.1. Associated with Ω_{sp^i} for $s \in \{1, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$ expression of corresponding Primitive Idempotent.

For $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$, we define $A_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^i}} \alpha^s$, $E_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^i}} \alpha^s$, $F_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^i}} \alpha^s$,

$G_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^i}} \alpha^s$, $H_i = p^i \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^i}} \alpha^s$. Then, $A_i, E_i, F_i, G_i, H_i \in GF(q)$.

Lemma 3.1.1. For cyclotomic cosets Ω_{ap^i} , $a \in \{\nu, \chi, \tau\}$, $0 \leq i \leq n - 1$, following holds:

$$a^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \Omega_{p^i} = a \Omega_{ap^i}$$

Proof. Since $\nu^2 = (1 + 6p^n)^2 = 1 + 36p^{2n} = 1 + 4p^n(9p^n + 3)$.

Since $p^n \equiv 1 \pmod{4}$, so $(9p^n + 3) \equiv 0 \pmod{4}$ and hence $\nu^2 \equiv 1 \pmod{16p^n}$

Therefore, $\nu^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \Omega_{p^i}$

Also, $\nu^2 \Omega_{p^i} = \{\nu^2 p^i, \nu^2 p^i q, \dots, \nu^2 p^i q^{\phi(p^{n-1})-1}\} = \nu(\nu p^i, \nu p^i q, \dots, \nu p^i q^{\phi(p^{n-1})-1}) = \nu \Omega_{\nu p^i}$

Thus, $\nu \Omega_{p^i} = \Omega_{p^i} = \nu \Omega_{\nu p^i}$

By similar argument result holds for χ and τ .

Lemma 3.1.2. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{\nu p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{\psi p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{\mu p^i s} \\ &= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0 & i + j \geq n \\ \frac{1}{p^j} A_{i+j} & i + j \leq n - 1 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 3.1.3. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{\psi p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\mu p^i s}$$

$$= \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0 & i+j \geq n \\ -\frac{1}{p^j} F_{i+j} & i+j \leq n-1 \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3.1.4. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\chi p^j}} \alpha^{\mu p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\zeta p^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\rho^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0 & i+j \geq n \\ -\frac{1}{p^j} G_{i+j} & i+j \leq n-1 \end{cases}$$

Lemma 3.1.5. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{p^i s} &= - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{\chi p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\rho^j}} \alpha^{\psi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\mu p^j}} \alpha^{v p^i s} \\ &= - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{\mu p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{\pi p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\pi p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0 & i+j \geq n \\ -\frac{1}{p^j} E_{i+j} & i+j \leq n-1 \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

Lemma 3.1.6. For $0 \leq i, j \leq n$,

$$\sum_{s \in \Omega_{\lambda p^j}} \alpha^{\lambda p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\nu p^j}} \alpha^{v p^i s} = \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\psi p^j}} \alpha^{v p^i s} = - \sum_{s \in \Omega_{\tau p^j}} \alpha^{\tau p^i s} = \begin{cases} 0 & i+j \geq n \\ -\frac{1}{p^j} H_{i+j} & i+j \leq n-1 \end{cases}$$

Theorem 3.1.1. The explicit expression for the primitive idempotent corresponding to $\Omega_{s p^i}$ for $s \in \{1, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \chi, \psi, \pi, \tau\}$ in R_{16p^n} are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{(1+4p^n)p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{v p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ &\quad - \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ &\quad - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} - A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\ &\quad - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+1}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+1}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \} \\ &\quad + p^{n-j-1} (8\bar{C}_{p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\lambda p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{vp^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} \\ &+ \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} \\ &+ E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} \\ &\phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \} \\ &+ p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j+1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j+1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\mu p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - a^{\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{\lambda^2 p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ &+ \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ &+ C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\ &+ G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \} \\ &+ p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j+1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j+1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\nu p^i}(x) &= \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 - \alpha^{p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ &- \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ &+ C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\ &+ F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \} \\ &+ p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j+1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j+1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\chi p^i}(x) = & \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{vp^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{2vp^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{\mu p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ & - \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ & - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{vp^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2vp^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \\ & + H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\rho p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \} \\ & + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\psi p^i}(x) = & \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{\mu p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} - \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} - \alpha^{vp^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ & \alpha^{\mu p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ & + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{vp^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2vp^i} - G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} - A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \\ & - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\rho p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \} \\ & + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\pi p^i}(x) = & \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ & + \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} - \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} + \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ & - C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{vp^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2vp^i} - A_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} + E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \\ & + F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\rho p^i} \} + \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} - \bar{C}_{8p^i} + \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} \} \\ & + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}})] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \theta_{\pi^i}(x) = & \frac{1}{16p^n} [\phi(p^{n-j}) \{ \bar{C}_0 + \alpha^{\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{p^n} + \alpha^{2\lambda p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2p^n} - \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^n} - \bar{C}_{8p^n} + \alpha^{\lambda^2 p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^n} \\ & + \alpha^{2p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^n} + \alpha^{4p^{n+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^n} \} - \frac{1}{p^j} \sum_{i=0}^{n-j-1} \{ E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{p^i} - D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2p^i} + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\lambda p^i} - B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} \\ & + C_{i+j} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} - F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\mu p^i} + D_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\mu p^i} + G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\nu p^i} + B_{i+j} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} - E_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\chi p^i} - H_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\psi p^i} + F_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\pi p^i} \\ & - G_{i+j} \bar{C}_{\tau p^i} \} - \phi(p^{n-j}) \sum_{i=n-j}^{n-1} \{ \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4p^i} + \bar{C}_{8p^i} - \bar{C}_{16p^i} - \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{4p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{4\lambda p^i} + \alpha^{2p^{i+j}} \bar{C}_{2\nu p^i} \} \\ & + p^{n-j-1} (\bar{C}_{8p^{n-j-1}} - \bar{C}_{16p^{n-j-1}}) \} \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Proof can be obtained by using lemmas 3.1.1 to 3.1.6. and similar procedure as that of Theorem 2.2.1.

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